

DETERMINING THE QUALITY OF THERAPY FOR TREATMENT OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS IN ADOLESCENTS

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Annation: this article attempts to reveal the main reasons for the effectiveness and safety of the use of comfodermK cream (methylprednisolone aceponate 0.1%) and tacropic ointment 0.03% (tacrolimus 0.03%) for the treatment of manifestations of atopic dermatitis on the face. To carry out scientific work, the author evaluated the results of treatment was carried out in 12 patients, aged 6 to 13 years, with a diagnosis of atopic dermatitis, the childhood period was moderate. The problem in question is still little studied, therefore, requires more thorough research.

Key words: komfodermK, tacrolimus, atopic dermatitis.

Introduction: Atopic dermatitis (AtD, atopic eczema, atopic eczema/dermatitis syndrome) — chronic allergic dermatitis; a disease that develops in individuals with a genetic predisposition to atopias, has a relapsing course, age-related features of clinical manifestations. It is characterized by exudative and (or) lichenoid rashes, increased serum IgE levels and hypersensitivity to specific (allergenic) and nonspecific stimuli. It has a clear seasonal dependence: in winter - exacerbations or relapses, in summer - partial or complete remissions. The prevalence of AD among developed countries is 10-20%. The manifestation of AD symptoms in children is observed at the age of 6 months in 60% of cases, up to 1 year in 75%, up to 7 years in 80-90%. Over the past decades, there has been a significant increase in the incidence of AD, its course is becoming more complicated, and the outcome is aggravated. In the 20th century, the connection between AtD, pollinosis and bronchial asthma was

confirmed, which was designated by the term "atopic triad" [2]. The combination of AD with bronchial asthma is observed in 34% of cases, with allergic rhinitis - in 25%, with hay fever - in 8%. AD may be the debut of an "allergic march", when further atopic diseases develop in such patients: food allergy, bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis. AD associated with food allergy accelerates the progression of the "allergic march".

Objective: to study the efficacy and safety of using comfodermK cream (methylprednisolone aceponate 0.1%) and tacropic ointment 0.03% (tacrolimus 0.03%) for the treatment of manifestations of atopic dermatitis on the face.

Materials and methods: evaluation of the results of treatment was carried out in 12 patients aged 6 to 13 years with a diagnosis of atopic dermatitis, the childhood period was moderate. Pale, dry skin with peeling of the face, with erythematous-squamous foci was observed in all patients. Ophthalmic manifestations were also recorded in 100% (eyelid dermatitis in 11 (92%), periorbital hyperpigmentation in 7 (58%), Denier-Morgan folds in 5 (42%), blepharitis in 3 (25%), dacryocystitis in 1 (8%). In addition, 2 patients had rarefaction of the outer third of the eyebrows (17%), cheilitis in 4 (33%), angular stomatitis in 2 (17%). days. In the last two days of applying cream comfoderm K, the use of tacropic ointment 0.03% 1 time per day was additionally started, and then after the cancellation, tacropic ointment was used 2 times a day for an average of 10 days, then the use was reduced to 1 time per day until complete symptoms disappeared (average 12 days). Maintenance therapy according to the scheme 2 times a week was prescribed to 5 patients, in 7 patients only emollients were subsequently used.

Results: removal of exacerbation occurred in 100%. Minor symptoms of skin irritation on the use of Tacropic ointment were observed in 7 patients at the beginning of the application, but this did not require discontinuation of the drug. Subsequent control examinations were carried out monthly for 6 months. There was no recurrence in the group of patients receiving maintenance therapy. In

patients receiving only basic therapy, exacerbation was recorded in 3 patients. Maintenance therapy was prescribed to one patient. The other two received episodic therapy to relieve exacerbation according to the scheme Tacropic ointment 0.03% 2 times a day. Skin atrophy at the sites of drug application was not observed.

Conclusions: the consistent use of Komfoderm K cream and Tacropic ointment 0.03% in the treatment of manifestations of atopic dermatitis on the face showed high efficiency in relieving symptoms of exacerbation, most patients achieved long-term remission, showed good tolerability, side effects and no complications.

Figure-1 number of observed pathology and scores (%).

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